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Oxidation of Carbon Monoxide over Perovskite-like-LaMn₂Co_{1-x}O₃ Catalysts

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MODERNIZATION has inevitably brought in pollution. In urban areas, motor vehicles account for probably more than 50% of pollutants like carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides. Thus, development of automotive exhaust catalysts has assumed importance. Recently, solid state chemistry is increasingly being brought to bear on the formulation of catalytic materials. Around 1970, cobaltite perovskites were suggested as substitutes for the costlier and rarer noble metals¹. Encouraging results were obtained with LaCoO₃ and LaMnO₃ in the oxidation of carbon monoxide and the reduction of nitric oxide^{2,3}. However, the feasibility of the mixed LaMnO₃-LaCoO₃ system has apparently not been investigated so far. In this article, the results of oxidation of carbon monoxide over these mixed catalysts are reported and discussed.

Experimental

Several samples with the nominal composition LaMn₂Co_{1-x}O₃, 0 ≤ x ≤ 1, were synthesized by heating appropriate mixture of oxalates of lanthanum, cobalt and manganese in an atmosphere of

oxygen at 900-1000° for several hours. Formation of single phase compounds with perovskite-like structure was confirmed through analysis of X-ray powder diffractogrammes using CuK_α (λ = 1.5418 Å).

Catalytic activity was determined in a flow reactor employing a feed gas of composition 5%CO, 5%O₂ and 90%N₂. Carbon monoxide was prepared by the dehydration of formic acid with conc. sulphuric acid. Commercial grade oxygen and nitrogen gas, supplied in cylinders by Indian Oxygen Ltd., Bombay were used. However, these gases were individually purified further by passing through various traps (like sodium hydroxide for the removal of carbon dioxide in carbon monoxide, heated copper turnings at 400° for the removal of oxygen in nitrogen, etc.) and each gas was then analysed, using gas chromatograph, to be of 99.9% pure. The individual gas flow rates were controlled by using flow-meters and needle valves and mixed in a glass bulb. The composition of the mixture was checked using the gas chromatograph before passing through the catalyst bed. The space velocities used were between 19,000-25,000 ml/h-ml of catalyst. The feed gas and the products were analyzed on an on-line gas chromatograph. The temperature range was between 200-350°.

Results and Discussion

The preparative conditions and the X-ray data of the compositions are given in Table 1. It can be noted that all the compositions belong to the rhombohedral system and that the unit cell volume increases regularly with increasing manganese content. The activation energy and the frequency factor for the oxidation of carbon monoxide is also summarised in Table 1. The variation of the rate of oxidation (R_i) with temperature is shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 depicts the variation of percentage conversion with temperature.

For pure LaMnO₃, the catalytic activity was negligible. For isothermal conditions, the activity increased with increasing cobalt content and only slightly after x ~ 0.4. The constancy of activation energy values indicates that the mechanism of catalytic action presumably remains the same. In general, the conversion corresponding to maximum

TABLE 1—STRUCTURAL AND KINETIC DATA FOR THE SYSTEM LaMn₂Co_{1-x}O₃

X	Preparative conditions		Rhombohedral lattice parameters			Activation energy E _a k cal.mole ⁻¹	Frequency factor A (S ⁻¹)
	Sintering temperature (°C)	Duration of sintering (days)	a (Å)	c (°)	v (Å ³)		
0.0	1000	4	7.665	90.5	450.25	19.70	2.24 × 10 ⁺⁸
0.3	1000	8	7.719	90.5	459.83	18.25	9.55 × 10 ⁺¹
0.5	1000	4	7.774	89.9	469.73	20.65	8.92 × 10 ⁺²
0.6	900	4	7.794	89.8	473.46	21.20	1.82 × 10 ⁺²

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Fig. 1. Arrhenius plots for the oxidation of carbon monoxide over $\text{LaMn}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{O}_3$ catalysts. (—○— $\text{LaMn}_{0.6}\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{O}_3$; —▽— $\text{LaMn}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{O}_3$; —△— $\text{LaMn}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{O}_3$; —□— LaCoO_3)

Fig. 2. Percentage conversion of carbon monoxide vs temperature over $\text{LaMn}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{O}_3$ catalysts, at a flow rate of 8000 ml/hr. (—□— $\text{LaMn}_{0.6}\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{O}_3$; —△— $\text{LaMn}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{O}_3$; —○— LaCoO_3)

catalytic activity decreased from about 90% at 350° to nearly 50% at 250°. The results can be discussed on the basis of spin states of the concerned transition metal ions and non-stoichiometry resulting from variations in the proportion of cation/anion vacancies.

Lanthanum manganite is oxygen excess especially when prepared in oxygen atmosphere and reported to have Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} ions, the concentrations of which are very much dependent on the preparative conditions⁴. In this 'hopping' type material the presence of Mn^{3+} or Mn^{4+} or cation vacancies in the La(A) site apparently do not contribute to catalytic activity, as experimentally observed. On the other hand, lanthanum cobaltite is oxygen deficient⁸ and known to contain

cobalt ions in multivalent states⁶, viz., Co^{3+} , Co^{4+} (high spin), Co^{5+} (low spin) and Co^{6+} in the temperature region where catalytic activity was studied. Presence of the transition metal ions in different oxidation states viz., Mn^{4+} , Mn^{3+} , Co^{3+} and Co^{4+} in the system $\text{LaMn}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{O}_3$ has also been suggested by Jonker⁷. Since one may expect a decrease in the oxygen vacancies with increase in manganese content in the solid solutions between LaCoO_3 and LaMnO_3 , the negligible activity shown by the compositions of $x > 0.6$ may be attributed to the oxygen vacancies in the compound.

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Ruthenium(III) Catalysed Oxidation of Chalcones by Ce(IV) in H_2SO_4 -HOAc Mixtures: A Kinetic Study

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IN an earlier communication¹ we reported the kinetics of oxidation of chalcone (benzalacetophenone) and its substituted analogues by Ce(IV) in H_2SO_4 -HOAc mixtures. This reaction, which is extremely slow at room temperature, was found to be catalysed by as small amounts of Ru(III) as 10^{-7} M. For example, under similar conditions the rate constant values (k'') for uncatalysed and catalysed reactions are 3.2×10^{-6} and 4.07×10^{-4} lit.mol⁻¹.sec⁻¹, respectively at 300 K. Ru(III) was employed as a homogeneous catalyst in Ce(IV) oxidation of a variety of compounds and various mechanisms were proposed²⁻⁴. Since chalcone

contains two functional groups viz., >C=C< and >C=O in conjugation, it is of interest to find out the type of mechanism when it reacts with Ce(IV) in the presence of Ru(III). It is therefore worth considering (i) whether the presence of Ru(III) ion results in a change in the mechanism, (ii) the nature of the radicals or ions formed and (iii) the effect of substituents on rate of reaction. The present study is a step in this direction.